

Researching experiences of mathematics: Black/feminist and queer lenses

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This symposium will explore how critical methodologies in mathematics education shed light on the sociohistorical, political, and cultural role of mathematics in shaping experiences of learning mathematics. Drawing from Black/feminist and queer theories, panelists and participants will consider the subjective experiences of learners that tend to be obscured in research, and how critical shifts in methodology might bring such stories to light.

Aims of the symposium

In the last four decades, research in mathematics education has seen a shift toward an examination of the cultural practice of mathematics and of the identities and subjective experiences that unfold in and through this culture (Darragh, 2016). Decentering achievement, this research has sought instead to consider the role of mathematics—as a historical, political, and cultural institution—in engendering particular learner experiences in formal STEM spaces (e.g., Mendick, Berge, & Danielsson, 2017). As such work has been primarily concerned with surfacing as-yet untold stories of learners in mathematics, it has simultaneously fostered the development of a variety of critical methods in mathematics education research.

The Mathematics Education and Society conferences and the wider MES community have been at the heart of this shift. However, feminist, intersectional and queer perspectives have been less commonly taken up here than in the wider critical education research literature. This symposium will address this gap by offering three examples of these perspectives in action in order to open up discussion on what they offer for research into mathematics education.

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Relevance

Scholars within the MES community have championed the perspective that mathematics is a cultural and political practice and that mathematics education is governed by neoliberal and imperialistic interests (Gutiérrez, 2013; Pais & Valero, 2012). For example, Mendick, Berge, and Danielsson (2017) made sense of the identities of two students in a Swedish upper-secondary science program in terms of “active accomplishments, neither fixed nor singular but multiple and fractured, and as coming into being through talk, actions, and relationships” (p. 486). Through multi-modal micro-analysis we see how students positioned themselves in and are positioned by neoliberal discourses around equity in STEM. Sengupta-Irving and Vossoughi (2019) located their analysis in the view that equitable STEM educational policies are sustained by U.S. hegemonic agendas that shape the gendered and racialized experiences of minoritized girls. In spite of this, the authors found that participants were able to reclaim science with “ingenuity and humanity” (p. 495), refusing the prescription of science as primarily for U.S. hegemony.

Such studies surface important stories—both about learners and about STEM institutions—that have fallen by the wayside. Dotson (2014) argued that stories go untold due to our “inclination to understand oppression as we experience it and to extend our analysis of it beyond what we ourselves can see from our particular vantage point” (p. 57). Importantly, most “socioepistemic orientations towards oppression will illuminate as much as they obscure” (p. 45). Ahmed (2006) wrote similarly about orientation: “some things are relegated to the background in order to sustain a certain direction; in other words, in order to keep attention on what is faced. Perception involves such acts of relegation that are forgotten in the very preoccupation with what it is that is faced” (p. 31). That is, attending to something necessarily implies not attending to something else. Thus our work as researchers demands regular reflection and recalibration, which we hope to engage in at this symposium. We ask: what stories does our vantage as researchers render “theoretically invisible” (Dotson, 2014, p. 46)? And how might Black/feminist and queer perspectives bring these stories to light?

Format of the symposium

The symposium will begin with three provocations that present some possibilities of using Black/feminist and queer lenses on mathematics experiences.

Provocation 1

Maisie Gholson will offer new epistemological methods to resist deficit-perspectives on Black learners in mathematics education research. Expanding on earlier work in Gholson & Martin (2019), she centers performativity and pain to illuminate some of the ways in which mathematics education is “violent, painful, and dehumanizing” (p. 393) to Black learners. Through an examination of the repetitive and resistive identity-based performances and gestures of Black girls, Gholson is interested in methods that animate the oppressive

structures that operate within the mathematics classroom. Adopting Dotson's (2014) theory of oppression as a "multistable" phenomenon — which renders subjective experiences of oppression theoretically invisible in research — she argues that intersectional phenomenological lenses are crucial to telling such stories, while also helping demonstrate the broader politics of mathematics as raced, classed, and gendered.

Provocation 2

Sarah Radke's perspective seeks to disrupt dominant notions of learning and identity development as spatially and temporally linear. It builds on her collaborative work in Ma, Kelton, Radke, & Della Volpe (2020), in which a cross-setting analysis of participation illuminated how the "relational practices" (p. 259) of one youth were not merely incidental to a moment of statistical learning, but rather instrumental to it. Drawing on Butler's conception of performativity as contextual and structured by powered relations (1990), Radke's analytic lens is, in part, a response to Langer-Osuna and McKinney de Royston's (2017) call for tools to study how power mediates learning and positioning at multiple time-scales. Drawing from—and complicating—Saxe's (1991) focus on shifts in form-function relations across interactions, this view attends to the cultural, political, and social construction of a repertoire of forms across space and over time. Radke inspires us to reconsider where and how we look for learning, opening up the possibility that moments of learning and identity development are dispersed across experiences and interactions.

Provocation 3

Heather Mendick will speak about a research project with Eva Silfver, Maria Berge and Andreas Ottemo about contemporary geek identities. The data will be the opening sequences of the 2008 film *Iron Man*. These illustrate how mathematical, scientific and technological expertise is being repositioned. Previously the dominant image of the math/science/tech genius was a physically-weak socially-awkward geeky white man. Tony Stark / Iron Man exemplifies a new entrepreneurial configuration of the genius. While still geeky, white and male, he is both physically strong and socially confident. A queer poststructural reading of this geek entrepreneurial masculinity illuminates how it legitimates gender, economic and neo-colonial power relations, and represents a shift in hegemonic masculinity in which previously marginalised 'geeky' traits carry new status.

Symposium Structure

Participants and panelists will reflect on these provocations, sharing their own critical orientations to and analyses of the data. Following an initial discussion, panelists will describe the potential of their particular conceptual lenses for mathematics education research. Finally, the group will be encouraged to explore what intersectional, feminist, and queer lenses bring.

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